

Hybrid rice—a biovillage experience

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Rice cultivation today faces the tough challenge of feeding an ever-increasing world population using shrinking resources. The scenario in a group of 19 villages in Pondicherry (south India), where the biovillage model is implemented by the M.S. Swaminathan Research Foundation, looks all the more grim with stagnating rice yields (5 t ha^{-1}) at very high input use (200 kg N ha^{-1}) in the irrigated transplanted system. The biovillage model seeks ways of addressing concurrently problems on natural resource conservation, household food security, and rural development. The model ensures sustainable productivity of the physical resource base as indicated by a baseline survey. To overcome these constraints, a participatory evaluation of the potential of hybrid rice in the biovillages was undertaken.

The methodology adopted included yield testing of rice hybrids released by research institutions through the farmers' participatory approach and demonstrations and field days to popularize test hybrids. Participatory evaluation of hybrids was done during seasonal evaluation meetings for trial farmers and during demonstrations. A survey of 100 farmers was also conducted to confirm evaluation results.

Around 60 trials were conducted to yield-test 12 hybrids over a 3-y period during dry seasons (*Naravai* [Jan-Apr] and *Sornavari* [May-Aug]) and the wet season (*Samba* [Sep-Jan]). Survey results show what farmers perceive to be the advantages and disadvantages of hybrids.

The advantages of hybrid rice include

- Higher yield (6–20% increase over local check variety)
- Farmers are motivated to adopt other management practices. (A marked reduction in the number of seedlings hill⁻¹ from 8–10 to 3–4 and line planting were the significant

changes in cultivation practices observed.)

The disadvantages cited were

- The harvest could not be used as seeds for the next season
- Poor cooking quality of hybrids
- Higher seed cost of hybrids (by 60%) over inbred varieties and problems of seed availability
- Traders prefer inbred varieties (10–13%) over hybrids
- Less head rice recovery of hybrids (10–13% less than that of inbred varieties)
- 10–15% higher cost due to higher priced seed, weeding in nursery plot (due to lesser seed rate), and additional labor required for transplanting 1–2 seedlings hill⁻¹.
- Narrow yield advantage of some hybrids over inbred varieties (at least 20% yield advantage needed)
- Lesser grain weight (1,000-grain weight of 19.0 g for hybrids vs 20.8 g for inbred varieties)

About 40% of the farmers preferred hybrid rice, but the rest said they would choose hybrids if the disadvantages were overcome. An analysis of these two categories of farmers indicates that

1. Hybrid rice was preferred by farmers who
 - belong to the marginal and small farmer category and generally have low harvests ($3.5\text{--}4 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$),
 - involve family labor in crop management and thus have a lower cultivation cost,
 - generally use inferior-quality seeds and therefore use a high seed rate (185 kg ha^{-1}) with inbred varieties,
 - sell their harvest without processing, and
 - rank grain yield more important than quality.

2. Hybrid rice was not preferred by
 - varietal seed producers who realize high income from seed production activities, and
 - large farmers who find it difficult to transplant 1–2 seedlings hill⁻¹ due to labor scarcity.

Based on these results, we conclude that marginal and small farmers are the potential target groups for hybrid rice, whereas women's groups could be trained to engage in hybrid rice seed production as a source of livelihood.

Farmers emphasized the need for participatory breeding of hybrids with a yield advantage of at least 20% over inbreds, better cooking quality, and lower seed cost. They also stressed the importance of ecofriendly management practices (e.g., blending organic with inorganic components in nutrient management) and standardizing drum seeder techniques to reduce labor demand to stimulate the use of hybrid rice in the biovillages.

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